

end of the season and signify acute moisture stress at the panicle initiation stage of the reproductive phase to the ripening phase of a wet season rice crop.

The possibility of a 3 wk continuous drought is nearly the same throughout the season. An up to 1 wk duration of maximum drought, however, is normally

distributed and is more likely at the intermediate growth stage than at other stages. Extreme drought of 7-wk duration is rare. □

Farming systems

Fish output effects on rice yield in a rice-fish farming system in Luzhou Region, China

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The percentage of rice yield increase (PRYI) went from -11.7 to 8.1 and fish output from 0.3 to 2.25 t/ha in 13.1 ha in Luzhou in 1987. The PRYI was negatively and significantly correlated with fish output, where $y = 11.5529 - 10.3368x$, $n = 9$, and $r = -0.9951^{**}$. We conducted studies in 1988-89 to learn why rice yields decreased with a large fish output in a rice-fish farming system.

We planted hybrid rice Shanyou 63 in a 20- × 13-m plot in a randomized block design. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. A cross furrow, 0.5 m deep and 0.4 m wide, was made. Its area represented 10% of that of the plot. Fish fry, each weighing 50 g, were released at a ratio of 3 carp:5 grass carp:2 crucian carp.

We transplanted rice seedlings in mid-April at 1 seedling/hill, spaced 26 × 13 cm. Maximum tillering occurred before June, and the crop matured in mid-August. June to August is the best time for fish growth in Luzhou. In the low fish output system, fish fry were released in mid-June and harvested in October. Tillering was not inhibited, because at the 2- to 3-cm water depth, fish loosen the soil and control weeds and insect pests while feeding. Incorporating fish in ricefields increased 1,000-grain weight, spikelets per panicle, and seed setting percentage (see table).

In a rice-fish farming system with large fish output, fry must be released in April to fully utilize light and temperature resources during fish growth. Irrigated ricefields with water depth of 15 cm inhibited tiller production and decreased productive panicles. This decreased grain yield but

Effect of fish output on grain yield in rice-fish farming system.

Treatment	Seedlings transplanted (no./m ²)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Productive panicles (no./m ²)	Seed set (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Fry (no./m ²)	Fish wt increase (g/fry per d)	Fish output (t/ha)
<i>1988</i>								
Rice-fish	52	383	270	89.6	7.6	0.5	1.5	1.6
Rice alone	52	545	351	86.6	8.8	—	—	—
Rice-fish	28	470	274	89.4	8.3	0.3	1.3	0.9
Rice alone	28	521	287	87.1	7.8	—	—	—
<i>1989</i>								
Rice-fish	51	390	274	76.8	6.6	0.5	2.4	2.1
Rice alone	51	555	338	74.9	7.2	—	—	—
Rice-fish	28	428	278	78.3	8.7	0.3	1.4	0.7
Rice alone	28	454	282	76.3	8.1	—	—	—

increased 1,000-grain weight, spikelets per panicle, and percentage of seed setting (see table).

Farmers should increase the number of transplanted seedlings, adopt rice

ridge culture for deeper water depth, and use rice varieties with high tillering ability to increase grain yield in rice-fish farming systems with large fish output. □

Farm machinery

The peristaltic pump: a promising, stream-driven, water-lifting device for agriculture

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Many farms in developing countries are predominantly rainfed. The availability of water during the dry season is a major constraint on agricultural productivity. Stream-driven pumps could make fields located above fast-flowing rivers or canals more productive.

We have developed and tested two pumps that make use of locally available materials: a spiral pump and a peristaltic pump.

Peristaltic pumps work on the simple principle of rollers rotating inside a stationary housing and pressing one or more elastomeric tubes against a cylindrical

housing wall. The rotation of the rollers alternately compresses and releases the tubing. After compression, the tubing recovers its original shape and creates a vacuum, which makes the pump self-priming (see figure).

The prototype uses the brake drum of a truck (30 cm inner diam) and the plate of a disk brake. Two types of 2.5-cm tubing were tested: an expensive imported neoprene and a cheap, locally available polyester-reinforced chemical hose.

The pump was installed above a water-filled drum and connected through a chain drive to a 1-hp, variable-speed electric motor. Tests under laboratory conditions used a varying number of rollers (2, 3, and 4) at different speeds of rotation (24, 36, 51, 62, 73 RPM), different clearances between the rollers and the brake drum (7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 mm), and different total static heads (0.4, 5.32, 8.42, and 10.53 m). Power requirements, flow rate, and

efficiency were determined for each combination of parameters.

All the tested parameters showed statistical interrelations. Efficiencies were highest at high static heads, slower speeds of rotation, with three rollers attached and with a clearance of 8 mm. The power required to rotate the pump increased with number of rollers, speed of rotation and static head, and with decreasing clearances.

The tube materials differed greatly in durability and performance. Efficiencies for neoprene tubing were about 30% at a high head, but at low speeds of rotation, its durability was drastically reduced due to bulging and finally bursting of the hose at the pump exit. An unused polyester-reinforced tube proved to have a much longer lifetime, even at low speeds and

high static heads. The number of rollers and the clearance, however, had significant effects on the self-priming abilities of this tubing.

With two rollers attached, a clearance of 9 mm, and a rotation speed of 36 RPM, the pump was self-priming even at a head of 10.53 m, but efficiency was drastically reduced by back-flow. With four rollers, the chemical hose was unable to self-prime. At an efficiency of about 36%, a maximum power of 59.8 W was needed to operate the pump with three rollers attached, a clearance of 8 mm, and 24 RPM to deliver about 11 liters/min to a head of 10.53 m. We predict that a stream flow of about 0.7 m/s can provide the required power of 60 W to drive this pump if attached to an

undershot waterwheel with an efficiency of 20% and a paddle surface area of 1 m²,

The efficiency of the pump decreased under the same experimental conditions to about 10% with an input power requirement of about 50 W. The polyester-reinforced chemical hose survived 1 million cycles of tube compression and self-restitution in a durability test at a static head of 10.53 m. This is equivalent to about 600 h or 25 days of continuous field operation at 10 RPM and three rollers. Ideally, a tube material with the combined flexibility of the neoprene tubing and the durability of the polyester-reinforced hose is needed.

An achieved efficiency of about 30% at high heads, combined with reduced power requirements at low rotation speeds, indicates the potential of the peristaltic pump. □

Front and half-section views of peristaltic pump with 3 sets of rollers.

ENVIRONMENT

Relationships among methane emission from flooded ricefields, solar radiation, straw incorporation, and yield

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Many questions exist about potential physiochemical changes in the atmosphere due to increased methane emissions from rice plants growing in flooded soil. We assessed some of the key factors influencing methane production and emission from typical silty-clay rice soils near Beaumont, Texas. We grew the cultivar Jasmine 85, which matures about 140 d after emergence from Apr plantings, under

conventional drill-seeded culture during 1990. We maintained 10 cm of water from about 30 d after emergence to about 10 d before harvest. We took weekly duplicate 30-min methane samples from 0.4-m² open-bottom chambers with rims that rested below the water surface.

Methane flux determinations showcu significant methane emission of at least 100 mg/m² per d through rice plants, beginning about 10 d after soil flooding.